

Structure and evolution of a debris cloud in the early phases

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Understand the structure and evolution with an exact calculation of spatial density

- Goal: understand the structure and evolution of debris from a fragmentation in the first couple dozen orbits.
- View: inertial space with a density of objects, instead of objects with ephemeris in inertial space.
- In the language of fluid dynamics, shift from *Lagrangian* view to *Eulerian* view.
- No assumptions or approximations, e.g. relative motion, Gaussian distribution.
- No sampling or Monte Carlo simulation (except initially).

Monte Carlo simulation

900 km sun-synch circular, 6×6 , NASA breakup model, after 24 hours

Bands: a simple explanation

- A structure immediately evident are the antipodal bands.
- Why are they there?
- These are *not* orbits, they are different objects on different orbits at a single time.

Motivation from two-body orbit dynamics

- Simplify to two-body dynamics.
- Simplify to tangential (one-dimensional) delta- v : like Hohmann transfers.
- Perigee or apogee at fragmentation point.
- At any given time t after the fragmentation, objects on the antipodal line have gone an odd multiple of $1/2$ period, so semimajor axis

$$a = \sqrt[3]{\mu \left[\frac{t}{(2N + 1)\pi} \right]^2}.$$

for some integer $N \geq 0$.

Bands by number of whole orbits

- Antipodal radial distance is therefore

$$\bar{r} = 2a - r = 2\sqrt[3]{\mu \left[\frac{t}{(2N + 1)\pi} \right]^2} - r.$$

- Even though there are a continuum of semimajor axes (and thus orbital periods) in the ensemble, only objects with certain values appear on the antipodal line at a given time.
- Extension to two dimensional (in-plane) delta- v given in paper.
- What about 3D? What about off the antipodal line?
- Generalize, but stay with two-body simulation because there's clearly interesting structure without introducing perturbations yet.

Exact computation for any time

- We want an exact calculation of the *density* of objects at any point at any time, for any input density of velocities at the fragmentation point.
- Full three dimensional input and output.
- *Transformation of variables* tells you how a density G_X transforms under a function $F : X \rightarrow Y$ to G_Y .
- The density at a point is the sum over the densities at the inverse images F^{-1} divided by the absolute value of the forward Jacobian determinant at those points

$$G_Y(y) = \sum_{x \in F^{-1}(y)} \frac{G_X(x)}{|\det J_F(x)|}.$$

- Jacobian is the matrix of partial derivatives.

Lagrange coefficients

- Propagate with Lagrange coefficients “ f and g functions”
- Functions of semimajor axis a and the change in true anomaly ΔE

$$f = 1 - \frac{a}{r_1}(1 - \cos \Delta E)$$

$$g = t - \sqrt{\frac{a^3}{\mu}}(\Delta E - \sin \Delta E)$$

$$\dot{f} = \frac{-\sqrt{\mu a} \sin \Delta E}{r_2 r_1}$$

$$\dot{g} = 1 - \frac{a}{r_2}(1 - \cos \Delta E),$$

- ΔE must include whole orbits $2\pi N$.

Forward Jacobian determinant

- Partial derivatives $\partial \vec{r}_2 / \partial \dot{\vec{r}}_1$ worked out by Battin and untangled by Arora et al. (2015).
- Straightforward algebraic calculation, once f , g , \dot{f} and \dot{g} are known.
- Jacobian determinant has units of cubic time, values around 10^{10}s^3 .
- Dividing into a density in velocity space yields a density in position space.

Inverse images: solve Lambert problem

- Find each possible velocity that can reach the specified point in the specified time.
- Since the initial location \vec{r}_1 is fixed, solve the two-body Lambert problem.
- Output of that solution a and ΔE .
- From the last two, compute $\dot{\vec{r}}_1$ using Lagrange coefficients f and g

$$\dot{\vec{r}}_1 = \frac{\vec{r}_2 - f\vec{r}_1}{g}.$$

Getting all the solutions

- It is important for the density transformation computation that *all* inverse images and therefore Lambert solutions be found.
- Include zero orbit $N = 0$, whole orbit $N > 0$ solutions.
- Include short way, long way.
- Include circular, elliptical, parabolic, hyperbolic, if there will be enough velocity.
- For bound orbits: one solution each short and long way for $N = 0$ and two each for $N > 0$.
- For whole orbit solutions, there is a minimum time, which increases as N increases; this gives an upper limit of N to search.
- Mathematical solutions and physical solutions; eliminate if part of the trajectory goes below the surface of the earth.

Density map

- For each elapsed time and each point on a grid, compute all inverse images, velocity \vec{r}_1 and $|\det J|$.
- Look up initial velocity distribution.
- Divide velocity density by $|\det J|$ and sum over inverse images, that gives density for that $\vec{r}_2(t)$.
- Do all points in a grid, render as image.
- Color scale in km^{-3} , logarithmic

- Step time to make the next frame in the animation.
- A different input (velocity) density can be computed quickly.

The simulated fragmentation

- Original orbit: 900 km circular.
- Computed densities in the original orbit plane.
- Left-right, range -20Mm opposite the fragmentation location \vec{r}_1 to $+10\text{Mm}$ in the direction of it.
- Down-up, range $\pm 15\text{Mm}$ perpendicular.
- Velocity distribution flat or “top hat” Δv : isotropic and uniform in magnitude, bounded by 2kms^{-1} .
- Animations
 - 1 Every minute for 3 hours.
 - 2 Every 15 minutes for 36 hours.

Initial formation (1 hour) banana shape and anti-pinch

Curve around to form band, outer tail moves off screen

Curve around to form band, outer tail moves off screen

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Pinch point and bands clear (24 hours)

3 hour simulation, 1 minute step per frame

- Initially, high density ball, as it orbits, spreads out and becomes less dense.
- First visible inhomogeneity in the density is antipodal, at the “anti-pinch line”.
- Soon, forms into a banana shape (including the stem!).
- Curves back toward pinch point, forming the first band.
- Meanwhile, the outer tail of the lowest density region is moving outward and getting less dense.
- Start to see the superposition of bands
- Notice band has an outer edge of high density immediately adjacent to the no-solution region (gap).

Anti-pinch line

- The “anti-pinch line,” or “anti-pinch wedge” as it has been called, is distinctly noticeable after about an hour.
- It is caused by the appearance of two $N = 0$ (zero orbit) solutions.
- Because the earth blocks long-way solutions that are too close to the original point, the double solution is only possible near the antipodal line.
- As the first (outer) band moves out of the field of view at about three hours, it takes with it most of that concentrated density.

24 hour simulation, 15 minute step per frame

- Front of density “band factory” wave cycles around at original orbit radius, creating new bands.
- As new bands are created and move outward, they overlap the old bands.
- The boundaries of the bands are clearly visible in this case as superposition of the individual densities.
- Between the bands, the zero-density gaps on the antipodal side start out very broad, and gradually fill in.
- At around 18 hours, the bands in the middle are just starting to completely overlap.

24 hour simulation, 15 minute step per frame, continued

- The “fronts” of the bands have a sudden drop off in density with increasing radial distance, from the very highest density to actually or almost nothing, while the climb back up in density is much more gradual.
- Perturbations will certainly alter the appearance, and likely have the effect of smearing together sharp density contrasts, most notably, the bands.

Exact, calibrated, density

- It is possible to do an exact calculation of spatial density using the transformation of variables method.
- Demonstrated for flat bounded “top hat” Δv fragmentation distribution, but not limited to that.
- There are many structures, some previously identified, many not, that can be seen.
- Structures and their evolution can be described qualitatively.
- This is just the beginning.

Same physics, new world

- For centuries, we have been doing *point dynamics* for orbits.
- Ephemeris, or Lagrangian view of orbiting objects.
- The technique introduced here is *cloud dynamics*, or density dynamics.
- It is the Eulerian view of orbital space.
- The same physics underlies both, but the patterns are completely different.